

Sri Ramakrishna's Pedagogy

Siharan Chakrabarty*

Swami Tattwasarananda**

*Research (Ph.D.) Scholar, Educational Studies, Swami Vivekananda Centre for Multidisciplinary Research in Educational Studies, University of Calcutta.

**Principal, Ramakrishna Mission Sikshanamandira, Belur Math

ABSTRACT : Sri Ramakrishna gave a new dimension to pedagogy-the parable pedagogy and catechetical teaching. This new perspective in teaching/learning process enriched the present behavioural science (Education). Sri Ramakrishna's 'Dakshineswar Vidyalyaya Curriculum' included a variety of discourses, alternating with songs, parables, visits to the 'city of joy', which included visits to circus, museum, theatre, temples and many other recreationally encapsulated spiritual items. He never adopted strait-jacket methods in teaching. The present study is an attempt to examine the language of Sri Ramakrishna's pedagogy, technique and fundamentality of his interpretation along with his parable methodology.

Keywords : Catechetical teaching, strait-jacket methods, syntax.

The concept of pedagogy is widely used in the sense as the 'science of teaching'. Teaching is a process of contributing to the growth of knowledge, skill, literature or art etc. It is an activity to train the students for creative thinking to face the challenges in their future life. Pedagogy in the area of educational sciences plays an important role to enhance the all round development of the learners.

In ancient Indian educational system pedagogy was there but it was not considered

distinctly and separately from education as is done now-a-days. After the introduction of modern education in India by the Europeans, pedagogy as a separate and distinct field of study came to be considered as the most important component in teaching learning process and the teachers have been following contemporary methods of teaching which are said to have evolved in the Western Countries (Biswas, 2013). It is indeed unfortunate that we rarely choose to highlight this indigenous philosophy of learning and teaching which evolved in India long

back and which we find in its culminating form in the pedagogy which Sri Ramakrishna used to take resort to so frequently. Thus, it is important to explore the pedagogy of Sri Ramakrishna equating it with Indian pedagogy and thereby making a quest for a new integrated approach of teaching at various levels of education in India today.

A good teacher does not give his student a list of 'do's' and 'don'ts'; on the contrary, he quietly and unobtrusively helps him choose the right course and reject the wrong one. Discipline is best when it is self-imposed. A child must increase his inner strength to protect himself from evils. The task of the teacher is to help the child develop this inner strength. He helps him do this by feeding his mind with good and positive thoughts. He never utters a word of discouragement even if the child errs; there is nothing but encouragement from him.

The best example of what a teacher should be like was Sri Ramakrishna who never adopted strait-jacket methods in teaching his disciples. He let each disciple follow his natural bent of mind, for he knew that each individual was unique. If a disciple tried to imitate others, he would discourage it. He would much rather have him commit blunders following his natural inclination than be right by imitating others. He knew one could not go against one's own nature for long. The inherent nature of man must assert itself sooner or later.

Another characteristic of Sri Ramakrishna was that he never lectured anybody; gently, with understanding and affection, he would guide the steps of his disciples so that they might grow to their fullness, to the limit of their capacities (Lokeswarananda, 2013).

Sri Ramakrishna used to say, "I'm the most uneducated person". By saying this he pointed at his being illiteracy. But he was not totally that. In that age and time, the handwriting of this Brahmin child was quite beautiful. He was also good in monetary calculations and copying from texts. Whatever little bit of Sanskrit recitation of the verses he knew and could do, he knew well and was good in reciting them. He made many to read aloud the religious texts, while he listened to them, and remember everything he heard. But most importantly, he tapped the sources of inherent knowledge, and advised people how to do it themselves. At the same time, he displayed great expertise in tapping the sources of immense knowledge inside himself and express it in folk language.

Whatever Sri Ramakrishna said in simpler day to day life was translation, transliteration and much more of what was in the scriptures. It is heard that while he was in *Samadhi*, he wriggled in pain if a singer sang out of tune. In his entire life, Sri Ramakrishna remained extremely in tune with life and the immense sources of knowledge. With passing time, people have realized more and more the truth and universality of everything he had said. The great Swami Vivekananda, while talking about him had said, "I feel like throwing into the Atlantic all the bookish knowledge I possess, and like an innocent and ignorant child sit at the feet of this Brahmin (Sri Ramakrishna) and gain knowledge."

Regarding Sri Ramakrishna's education, people often say that he never studied any books, so why should they or anyone else do so? Thus many try to conceal their unwillingness to study by citing his example. A small search for the truth shows how baseless this logic is.

Firstly, it is not true that Sri Ramakrishna did not at all know how to read and write. He could easily read texts and write nicely as well (his hand written manuscripts of Punthis like Subahur Pala, Yogaddyar Pala are still preserved the Museum at Belur Math).

Secondly, he had acquired vast knowledge through learning by listening and remembered what he listened to. If he heard something once, he never forgot that. In his childhood, he could remember and recite every dialogue of every play he watched. Naturally, he never needed to study books. While in Dakshineswar, he often asked others to read to him "Aadhyatmaramayana" and "Yogavashishtha", and he used to listen attentively.

Thirdly, Sri Ramakrishna himself acknowledged that though he could not talk in Sanskrit but he could understand even the subtler essence of discourses when Pandits used to be engaged in it in Sanskrit.

Fourthly, He was master in nature studies and could put them in paintings, sculptures etc.

Fifthly, Swami Saradananda in his 'Sri Ramakrishna: The Great Master' stated that though Sri Ramakrishna was a bit confused at *Subhankarioral* calculations, he was not bad in arithmetic.

Sri Ramakrishna's Parable-pedagogy:

Parables were generally neglected in pedagogical theory, and considered inferior to teaching by analysis, reasoning and deduction. But it seems parables are now being taken seriously as a very effective form of teaching. Parables make the teaching-learning process richer and deeper. And of course, we tend to

remember stories much better than abstract concepts.

Sri Ramakrishna taught through dialogue, stories, songs, metaphors etc. He too peppered his talks with many parables (Sarvapriyananda, 2009).

Pedagogical advantages of parables:

1. Simple expressions may convey deep wisdom:

Parables are a superior form of teaching which can convey a message more effectively than many other forms of teachings.

On 5th August 1882, Sri Ramakrishna told to Vidyasagar, "What Brahman is cannot be described. All things in the world—the Vedas, the *Puranas*, the *Tantras*, the six systems of philosophy—have been defiled, like food that has been touched by the tongue, for they have been read or uttered by the tongue. Only one thing has not been defiled in this way, and that is Brahman. No one has ever been able to say what Brahman is."

Then Vidyasagar remarked to his friends, "Oh! That is a remarkable statement. I have learnt something new today."

Sri Ramakrishna further explained this concept of wisdom by mentioning a simple parable. "A man had two sons. The father sent them to a preceptor to acquire the knowledge of Brahman. After a few years they returned from their preceptor's house and bowed low before their father. Wanting to measure the depth of their knowledge of Brahman, the father first questioned the elder boy. 'My child', he said, 'you have studied all the scriptures. Now tell me, what is the nature of Brahman?' The boy began to explain Brahman by reciting various

texts from the Vedas. The father did not say anything. Then he asked the younger son the same question. But the boy remained silent and stood with eyes cast down. No word escaped his lips. The father was pleased and said to him, ‘my child, you have understood a little of Brahman. What it is cannot be expressed in words.’”

On that very day Sri Ramakrishna discussed a high philosophical concept to a devotee pertaining to the nature of Brahman.

“The jnani gives up his identification with worldly things, discriminating, ‘Not this, not this’. Only then can he realize Brahman. It is like reaching the roof of a house by leaving the steps behind, one by one. But the vijnani, who is more intimately acquainted with Brahman, realizes something more. He realizes that the steps are made of the same materials as the roof: bricks, lime, and brick-dust. That which is realized intuitively as Brahman, through the eliminating process of ‘Not this, not this’, is then found to have become the universe and all its living beings. The *vijnani* sees that the Reality which is *nirguna*, without attributes, is also *saguna* with attributes (M, 1942).

2. The known leads to the unknown:

The golden rule in teaching is to go from the known to the unknown, from the near to the far, and from what is to what shall be. Through familiar images like- a mother serving various dishes to her children, potatoes jumping on the frying pan, water and ice, the river Ganga and its waves, Sri Ramakrishna easily conveys deep philosophical truths.

On 28th October, 1882, a Brahmo devotee asks Sri Ramakrishna, “Sir, why are there so many different opinions about the nature of God?”

Some say that God has form, while others say that He is formless. Again, those who speak of God with form tell us about His different forms. Why all these controversies?”

Sri Ramakrishna discussed this, referring to a most common example which expressed a deep unknown meaning.

He said, “A devotee thinks of God as he sees Him. In reality there is no confusion about God. God explains all this to the devotee if the devotee only realizes Him. You haven’t set your foot in that direction. How can you expect to know all about God?”

“Listen to a story. Once a man entered a wood and saw a small animal on a tree. He came back and told another man that he had seen a creature of a beautiful red colour on a certain tree. The second man replied: ‘When I went into the wood, I also saw that animal. But why do you call it red? It is green’. Another man who was present contradicted them, and insisted that it was yellow. Presently others arrived and contended that it was grey, violet, blue, and so forth and so on. At last they started quarrelling among themselves. To settle the dispute they all went to the tree. They saw a man sitting under it. On being asked, he replied: ‘Yes, I live under this tree and I know the animal very well. All your descriptions are true. Sometimes it appears red, sometimes yellow, and at other times blue, violet, grey, and so forth. It is a chameleon. And sometimes it has no colour at all. Now it has a colour, and now it has none.’”

“In like manner, one who constantly thinks of God can know His real nature; he alone knows that God reveals Himself to seekers in various forms and aspects. God has attributes; then again He has none. Only the man who lives

under the tree knows that the chameleon can appear in various colours, and he knows, further, that the animal at times has no colour at all. It is the others who suffer from the agony of futile argument" (M, 1942, p. 150).

3. Concrete leads to Abstract:

It is very difficult to formulate abstract ideas but quite easy to understand a story. People think anecdotally not in abstraction. Parables can communicate abstract truths through stories with a kind of effortless ease.

On 24th August 1882, Sri Ramakrishna told to M (Mahendranath Gupta), "The mind of the yogi is always fixed on God, always absorbed in the Self. You can recognize such a man by merely looking at him. His eyes are wide open, with an aimless look, like the eyes of the mother bird hatching her eggs. Her entire mind is fixed on the eggs, and there is a vacant look in her eyes. Can you show me such a picture?" (M, 1942, p. 113)

4. Parables are never ending stories:

Parables can be read and re-read continuously with new insights and new benefits for the reader. As we grow and mature in life, the same parables are understood in greater depth.

On 14th December 1882, Vijaykrishna asked Sri Ramakrishna, "Don't the teachings of the Brahmo Samaj bring men salvation?"

Sri Ramakrishna answered, "How is it ever possible for one man to liberate another from the bondage of the world? God alone, the Creator of this world-bewitching maya, can save men from maya. There is no other refuge but that great Teacher, Satchidananda. How is it ever possible for men who have not realized God or

received His command, and who are not strengthened with divine strength, to save others from the prison-house of the world?"

"One day as I was passing the Panchavati on my way to the pine-grove, I heard a bullfrog croaking. I thought it must have been seized by a snake. After some time, as I was coming back, I could still hear its terrified croaking. I looked to see what the matter was, and found that a water-snake had seized it. The snake could neither swallow it nor give it up. So there was no end to the frog's suffering. I thought that had it been seized by a cobra it would have been silenced after three croaks at the most. As it was only a water-snake, both of them had to go through this agony. A man's ego is destroyed after three croaks, as it were, if he gets into the clutches of a real teacher. But if the teacher is an 'unripe' one, then both the teacher and the disciple undergo endless suffering. The disciple cannot get rid either of his ego or of the shackles of the world. If a disciple falls into the clutches of an incompetent teacher, he doesn't attain liberation" (M, 1942, P. 168).

Language of Sri Ramakrishna's Pedagogy:

In the perspective of colonial Indian psyche the colonized was to follow syntax for making sentence meaningful. Rammohan Roy used to say 'as long as the verb of a sentence is not reached, do not treat it as the end of the sentence and do not try to comprehend its meaning'.

Thus it is the relationship between the subject and verb in which the basic meaning of a sentence is supposed to be embedded but Sri Ramakrishna interrupted the so called embedded meaning and intruded a new meaning which is just the opposite of the commonly understood

meaning when he said to M(Mahendranath Gupta):

“A maidservant in the house of a rich man performs all the household duties, but her thoughts are fixed on her own home in her native village. She brings up her master’s children as if they were her own. She even speaks of as ‘my Ram’ or ‘my Hari’. But in her own mind she knows very well that they do not belong to her at all.”

“The tortoise moves about in the water. But can you guess where her thoughts are? They are on the bank, where her eggs are lying. Do all your duties in the world, but keep your mind on God” (M, 1942, p. 81)

Sometimes Sri Ramakrishna expressed displeasure through his language about Kolkata and its people. We can mention here when Sri Ramakrishna told Master:

“That’s the one hobby of you Calcutta people—giving lectures and bringing others to the light! Nobody ever stops to consider how to get the light himself. Who are you to teach others? (M, 1942, p. 80)

When Sri Ramakrishna visited other old cities of India like Vaidyanathdham, Kasidham, Mathura, Vrindavan he was quite comfortable and happy in those traditional Indian towns. Then why was he so critical at times about Kolkata? Here lies the basic difference between the making of a traditional Indian town and the others developed by the colonizers. Kasi, Vrindavan and Mathura were developed with familial intimacy with the rest of India. But the city of Kolkata with negation with the rest of Bengal.

In colonial Calcutta we find two distinctly opposite modes of discourses—on one side the

language of law, the language of bureaucracy, the language of logic, argument, and on the other the language of feeling, the language of tears and emotions. Sri Ramakrishna belonged to second group of language. Here we may refer to the utterance of Sri Ramakrishna at the time Keshab Sen’s illness:

“I made a vow to worship the Mother with green coconut and sugar on Keshab’s recovery. Sometimes, in the early hours of the morning, I would wake up and cry before Her; ‘Mother, please make Keshab well again. If Keshab doesn’t live, whom shall I talk with when I go to Calcutta?’ And so it was that I resolved to offer Her the green coconut and sugar (M, 1942, p.79).

Sri Ramakrishna did not learn this mode of discourse from any Anglophile school but acquired from mythological text. This language cannot be learnt from cognitive faculty but from precious golden heart which Sri Ramakrishna had.

Our basic concern in the use of a language should not be its syntax alone (ability to connect the subject with the verb, the noun with the adjective and the verb with the adverb) it must connect a man with another man, a heart with another heart. The real cultivation of language and literature as we have seen in Sri Ramakrishna Kathamrita would be possible only in this direction (Mukhopadhyay, 2013).

Fundamentality of Sri Ramakrishna’s Interpretations:

Whatever we see in nature by our visual organ does not express deep meaning oftentimes because we are not able to put our mind in that object with inner meaning. But Sri Ramakrishna had receptive mind which used to catch the transcendental element of the phenomenal

reality. It is the mind which transforms raw information in to meaningful knowledge. Interpretation is a process of meaningmaking. Every one of us is an interpreter. We try to make sense of every bit of information that we taken in. The mind is a processing unit. The quality of the interpretation depends on the quality of the mind. Those with clear and mature minds are able to produce clear and mature interpretations. The interpretation and the interpreter are distinct and yet inseparable.

In the perspective of truly moral life-building it is necessary to concentrate the mind. To understand this crucial matter Sri Ramakrishna mentioned an unique sentence, "Yogi(sadhaka) is not under mind, the mind is under the Yogi." We are all servants of our mind but only the persevering persons can be the master of their mind. For being a perfect man we need to concentrate our mind first—it has been described by so many great persons. But in this journey Sri Ramakrishna moved a step further emphasizing not only concentrating the mind but also to practice good thinking. In this way Sri Ramakrishna's interpretation penetrated the deep meaning of the scripts so that it can reveal its relevance to the people.

How do the interpretations of Sri Ramakrishna help us? They do it in at least three ways.

First, the interpretations given by Sri Ramakrishna tell us a lot about himself and his concerns.

Second, the interpretations may help us connect the God-like person to our contemporary concerns and issues, thus revealing that the person has relevance beyond his or her time and social situation (Tyagananda, 2013).

Third, as Sri Ramakrishna taught through dialogue with the seeking persons they could understand the process of teaching which was considered as *Catechetical teaching influenced by the Upanishadic system of teaching*.

Above all Sri Ramakrishna's interpretations had immense attraction to all owing to his organized presentation.

Simplicity and Directness of Sri Ramakrishna's Teachings:

Sri Ramakrishna spoke only the language he knew, the language of an un-educated villager. It should be admitted that villagers rarely speak the things that Ramakrishna spoke and their words rarely make the impact that Ramakrishna's words did. What is the mystery? The mystery is that he was a *man of experience*. He was a man of experience in two ways. First, he had direct experience of spiritual matters and truths: the experience he had was enormously rich both in its sweep and depth. Secondly, he depended on experience to settle issues, if and when the need arose, rather than resorting to logical reasoning and rational argument (Mukhopadhyay Pradyot Kumar, 2013).

Impact of discourse analysis in Sri Ramakrishna's Teachings:

Discourse analysis is a rapidly growing and evolving field. The conceptual framework stands on three main aspects-(i) anything beyond the sentence (ii) language use and (iii) a broader range of social practice that includes non-linguistic and non-specific instances of language.

Charles Fillmore captured the essence of discourse by presenting the two following

sentences, each of which appeared as a sign at a swimming pool. One sign said *please use the toilets, not the pool*. The other sign said *pool for members only*. If we read separately, each sign is reasonable and understandable enough. But when the two sentences were read as if they were parts of a single discourse, the second sentence forces a reinterpretation of the first. Fillmore's example captures what we might call the gift of discourse: new meanings are created through the relationship between sentences. But it also illustrates what we might call the curse of discourse: since more than one meaning can be created; how do we decide which meaning is intended, is justifiable and/or makes the most sense? (Schiffrin, & Hamilton, 2001)

The Great Master Sri Ramakrishna followed different methods for *lokosiksha* (mass education). Among those methods discourse oriented method was a promising one. Very often he taught through interaction. Both ancient and modern Indian education systems owe much to the interaction method. In ancient Indian education system the preceptor followed *catechetical* teaching and in modern Indian education the counsellors guide the learners through interactive process which is derived from constructive method.

Interactional process can be grouped into two categories: ethnomethodological and interpretivist. The major distinction between the two is that ethnomethodologists have a strong preference for restricting analysis to what is actually observable. Interpretivists or interactionists on the other hand are prepared to bring other sources of data to bear on the analysis of interactional data.

Sri Ramakrishna's pedagogy belonged to the latter category. When he taught a subject he applied unique natural examples relating to that subject for the learner's easy understanding. For explaining the nature of good teacher Sri Ramakrishna collected and used a unique data from the living society.

On 28th October 1882 Sri Ramakrishna told a Brahma devotee, "there are three classes of physicians: superior, mediocre, and inferior. The physician who feels the patient's pulse and just says to him, 'Take the medicine regularly' belongs to the inferior class. He doesn't care to inquire whether or not the patient has actually taken the medicine. The mediocre physician is he, who in various ways persuades the patient to take the medicine, and says to him sweetly: 'My good man, how will you be cured unless you take the medicine? Take this medicine. I have made it for you myself'. But he who, finding the patient stubbornly refusing to take the medicine, forces it down his throat, going so far as to put his knee on the patient's chest, is the best physician. Like the physicians, there are three types of religious teachers. The inferior teacher only gives instruction to the disciples but makes no inquiries about their progress. The mediocre teacher, for the good of the student, makes repeated efforts to bring the instruction home to him, begs him to assimilate it, and shows him love in many other ways. But there is a type of teacher who goes to the length of using force when he finds the student persistently unyielding; I call him the best teacher (M, 1942, Pp. 147-48).

Findings

1. Parable pedagogy of Sri Ramakrishna draws insights and material from Indian pedagogy.

2. Sri Ramakrishna's catechetical teaching was influenced by the Upanishadic system of teaching.
3. Sri Ramakrishna stood for learner centric pedagogy while giving instructions to each one according to his needs.
4. The use of language should not be its syntax alone, it must connect a man with another man, a heart with another heart—which we have seen in Sri Sri Ramakrishna Kathamrita.
5. Sri Ramakrishna's words poured out from his direct experience and made organized presentation.
6. Sri Ramakrishna inoculated and resuscitated Indian pedagogy through his unique teaching method.

Conclusion

Today nomenclature of 'education' has already been changed and it is called 'behavioural science' which derived from the expertise of counsellor on learners' attitude. It is indeed baffling a fact how hundred and thirty three years ago Sri Ramakrishna taught in this way, understanding the needs and aspirations of the learners. Here lies the relevance of the teachings of Sri Ramakrishna. Truthfulness, efficiency, accountability, accessibility, creativity, humanistic attitude, entrepreneurship and reasoning—these qualities which have been embedded in the word 't e a c h e r' were manifested in zenith in the teachings of the Great Master Sri Ramakrishna.

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